

ANALYSIS OF PRIMES AND DEVELOPING CORRELATION MODEL BETWEEN THEM

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I. ABSTRACT

The prime numbers have a simple definition, but they are full of mathematical puzzles. One such unsolved mystery concerns the distribution of prime numbers among integers. At first glance, the distribution of primes seems erratic, but several trends are evident. The prime number theorem (PNT) in mathematics describes the asymptotic distribution of prime numbers among positive integers. It formalizes the intuitive idea that this occurs by precisely quantifying the rate at which primes become less frequent as they grow larger. Numerous studies looked at the connection between prime numbers and their hypotheses. In this study, the correlation between different primes has been observed and a JAVA programme for determining the correlation model was created.

Keywords: Correlation; Prime number theorem; Program; Distribution

II. INTRODUCTION

One of the reasons why primes are important in number theory is because they can be viewed as the basic building blocks of the natural numbers. The basic theorem of mathematics states that every integer can be factored into a single list of prime numbers. As a result, learning about numbers is essentially learning about prime number properties. Mathematicians have learned a lot about prime numbers over the years. One of Euclid's most famous arguments proves that there are infinitely many primes. Mathematicians developed the Prime Number Theorem in the nineteenth century. Theorem provides rough estimates of how many numbers, given a large natural number, are prime that are less than the provided number. Primes become rarer as numbers increase according to a general formula. Despite what we already know about primes, there are still a tonne of logically obvious theories about primes that haven't been proven or disproven. It is always necessary to find a conjecture for prime numbers that can be used to determine their distribution as well as to look for connections between them.

Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, & Uniyal discovered the occult connection between various primes and their analysis in various intervals, as well as the correlation between them (2022). Sharma, D. K., and Uniyal, A. S. (2021) defined super primes, perfect super primes, and non-super primes along with the frequency of each over a specific time period. According to Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, and Uniyal A.S. (2021), two prime numbers $P_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} = pqr$ and $P_{\gamma,\beta,\alpha} = rqp$ such that $P_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \neq P_{\gamma,\beta,\alpha}$ are known as multi-reverse primes. Here, p, q, and r are three different prime numbers with α , β , and γ digits respectively. Agarwal, S., and Singh (2021) discovered the Fibonacci prime distribution and produced a Java programme to find Fibonacci primes within a given range. It was also suggested to encrypt and decrypt data using Fibonacci primes. Compared to current encryption methods, the suggested solution offers a high level of security against unauthorized access.

Since any number can be factored as the product of primes, according to the fundamental theorem, Agarwal, S., and Uniyal, A.S. (2015) gave primes a special place in mathematics. The study looked at composite numbers that could be factored by pairs of non-

repeating primes. Specific distributions and their applications have been developed in the field of cryptography key systems. Debnath L. & Basu K. (2015) also discussed the distribution of prime numbers, prime number theorems, and the connection between Euler's and Riemann's zeta functions and prime numbers in addition to discovering the Fermat and Mersenne prime numbers. Multidimensional reverse primes were defined by Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, and Uniyal in 2022. They also created a linear regression model for various primes and a JAVA programme to find the linear regression model. This study found a model for correlation between the various primes to determine their relationship and also developed a JAVA programme to find the correlation.

III. DISTRIBUTION OF SUPER PRIMES AND NON-SUPER PRIMES

Sharma, D. K., and Uniyal, A. S. (2021) find the distribution of Super Primes and Non-Super Primes as shown in Table-1.

Table-1 Distribution of Super primes and Non-Super primes

Interval	No. of Super primes (x)	No. of Non-super primes (y)
[1-1000]	90	78
[1001-2000]	51	84
[2001-3000]	77	50
[3001-4000]	49	71
[4001-5000]	53	66
[5001-6000]	62	52
[6001-7000]	44	73
[7001-8000]	34	73
[8001-9000]	43	67
[9001-10000]	48	64

IV. CORRELATION BETWEEN SUPER PRIMES AND NON-SUPER PRIMES

Number of Super primes (x)	Number of Non-Super prime (y)	$d_x = x - A$ where A = 53	$d_y = y - B$ where B = 66	d_x^2	d_y^2	$d_x d_y$
90	78	37	12	1369	144	444
51	84	-2	18	4	324	-36
77	50	24	-16	576	256	-384
49	71	-4	5	16	25	-20
53	66	0	0	0	0	0
62	52	9	-14	81	196	-126
44	73	-9	7	81	49	-63
34	73	-19	7	361	49	-133
43	67	-10	1	100	1	-10
48	64	-5	-2	25	4	10
		$\sum d_x = 21$	$\sum d_y = 18$	$\sum d_x^2 = 2613$	$\sum d_y^2 = 1048$	$\sum d_x d_y = -318$

Here, $n = 10$

The correlation coefficient is given by,

$$r = \frac{n \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy}{\sqrt{[n \sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2]} \times \sqrt{[n \sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{10 \times (-318) - 21 \times 18}{\sqrt{26130 - 441 \times 324} \times \sqrt{10480 - 324}}$$

$$r = \frac{-3180 - 378}{-3558} = \frac{-3558}{160.278 \times 100.777} = \frac{-3558}{16152.336} = -0.22$$

There is a negative correlation between super primes and non-super primes.

V. DISTRIBUTION OF PRIMES AND SUPER PRIMES

The distribution of primes and Super Primes is shown in Table-2.

Table-2 Distribution of Primes and Super primes

Interval	No. of Primes (x)	No. of Super primes (y)
[1-10000]	1229	551
[10000-20000]	1033	368
[20000-30000]	983	449
[30000-40000]	958	334
[40000-50000]	930	331
[50000-60000]	924	376
[60000-70000]	878	344
[70000-80000]	902	252
[80000-90000]	876	360
[90000-100000]	879	288

VI. CORRELATION BETWEEN PRIMES AND SUPER PRIMES

Number of primes (x)	Number of Super prime (y)	$d_x = x - A$ where $A = 930$	$d_y = y - B$ where $B = 331$	d_x^2	d_y^2	$d_x d_y$
1229	551	299	220	89401	48400	65780
1033	368	103	37	10609	1369	3811
983	449	53	118	2809	13924	6254
958	334	28	3	784	9	84
930	331	0	0	0	0	0
924	376	-6	45	36	2025	-270
878	344	-52	13	2704	169	-676
902	252	-28	-79	784	6241	2212
876	360	-54	29	2916	841	-1566
879	288	-51	-43	2601	1849	2193
		$\sum d_x = 292$	$\sum d_y = 343$	$\sum d_x^2 = 112644$	$\sum d_y^2 = 74827$	$\sum d_x d_y = 77822$

Here, $n = 10$

The correlation coefficient is given by,

$$r = \frac{n \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy}{\sqrt{[n \sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2]} \times \sqrt{[n \sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{10 \times (77822) - 292 \times 343}{\sqrt{1126440 - 85264} \times \sqrt{748270 - 117649}} = \frac{678064}{\sqrt{1041176} \times \sqrt{630621}} = \frac{678064}{1020.38 \times 794.12} = \frac{678064}{810304.17} = 0.837$$

There is a positive correlation between primes and super primes.

VII. JAVA PROGRAM TO FIND THE CORRELATION BETWEEN VARIOUS PRIMES

```
import java.util.*;
import java.lang.*;
class Correlation
{
public static void main(String args[])
{
Scanner in=new Scanner(System.in);
double x[],y[],dx[],dy[],xx[],yy[],dxdy[];
double A,B,sumx=0,sumy=0,sumxx=0,sumyy=0,sumdxdy=0,r,nr,dr;
int i,n;
System.out.print("Enter number of values :");
n=in.nextInt();
x =new double[n];
y =new double[n];
dx =new double[n];
dy =new double[n];
xx =new double[n];
yy =new double[n];
dxdy =new double[n];
System.out.print("Enter values of x :");
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
{
x[i]=in.nextDouble();
}
System.out.print("Enter values of y :");
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
{
y[i]=in.nextDouble();
}
System.out.print("Enter assumed mean of series x :");
A=in.nextDouble();
System.out.print("Enter assumed mean of series y :");
B=in.nextDouble();
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
{
dx[i]=x[i]-A;
dy[i]=y[i]-B;
xx[i]=dx[i]*dx[i];
yy[i]=dy[i]*dy[i];
dxdy[i]=dx[i]*dy[i];
sumx=sumx+dx[i];
sumy=sumy+dy[i];
sumxx=sumxx+xx[i];
sumyy=sumyy+yy[i];
}
```

```
sumxdy=sumxdy+dxdy[i];  
}  
nr=n*sumxdy - sumx*sumy;  
dr=Math.sqrt(n*sumxx-(sumx*sumx))*Math.sqrt(n*sumyy-(sumy*sumy));  
r=nr/dr;  
System.out.println("Total Numbers :"+n+"\nCorrelation Coefficient :"+r);  
}  
}
```

VIII. CONCLUSION

The correlation between different primes is examined in this study, which is useful for determining their relationship and for the development of a conjecture regarding the distribution of various primes. The investigation of the intricate relationship between various primes will be aided by a JAVA programme that has been created to determine the correlation between the prime numbers.

IX. REFERENCES

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